

Altering the Emergence of a Fallow State in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: Channeling Human Resources for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The study focused on altering the emergence of a fallow state in Nigeria's fourth republic through channelling its human resources for sustainable development. The objective of the research was to develop an explanatory model that explores the available alternative paths that countries facing human resources management challenges can adopt to alter the possibility of emerging as a fallow state or necessary entering into it. Utilising Marxism to extrapolate the inherent human resources conditions and predictive revolutionary outburst (which is failing to occur in Nigeria) and Ekeh's theory of 2 republics to explain how complex dialectical social interactions provide sufficient conditions to allow Nigeria's perennial decline and decay towards the possibility of a fallow state. The researcher adopted quantitative method, utilising human capital index, human development index and migration data to make correlation analysis to measure the quality of institution that manages human resources in Nigeria and examined the pattern of flight against the postulation of a fallow state. The researcher recommended that there is need to urgently develop a 50 year national human resources investment and development strategy to aggressively channel Nigeria towards sustainable development.

Keyword: Fallow State, Human Resource Capital, Human Resource Management, Institution and Sustainable Development

Introduction and Motivation for the Study

Nigeria's fourth republic that commenced in 1999 and has subsisted up till 2020, stretching a period of twenty-one years of democratic experiment have troubling challenges that threaten its survival as a political entity. Okotoni (2017) explored and identified that Nigeria is trapped in governance crisis and state failure, preventing it to effectively function. The country has manifested decaying institutions that excluded majority of the citizens/population from participating in both political and economic institutions that would have allowed for sustainable development to occur (Fukuyama, 2011, 2014; Acemoglu & Robinson 2013).

Disquieting at this point is that Nigeria's current population is estimated at 202,886,491 people as at 15/11/2019 and by 2050, it is projected to reach 401,315,000 with 50.67% male and 49.33% female. Births per day is 20,496 and deaths per day is 6,398 leaving a net change per day of 13,934 and a net migration per day of 164 (<http://worldpopulationreview.com>, <https://www.worldbank.org>). Nigeria's economy is

heavily dependent on crude oil sales and its price volatility coupled with an agricultural sector engaging majority of the rural population (about 80% of the country's population) that is already poor and threatened by the herdsman-farmer crisis. Inflation rate is at 11.6%, captured with unemployment and underemployment of 23% and 20% respectively, which readily explains why half of Nigeria's population (101 million) is trapped in extreme poverty and it is estimated to reach 120 million by 2050. (<http://worldpopulationreview.com/countries/nigeria-population>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Poverty_in_Nigeria). The state of poverty reflects the level of human capital investment a country has allowed to foster over time. Consequently, low human capital investment has relationship with poverty and more significantly, an intolerable level of poverty or excruciating poor human conditions will naturally induce migration causing a fallow state to emerge (Ogundipe & Lawal 2013; Hagen-Zanker, Poster & Vidal 2017; Obayori, Udeorah & Aborh, 2018).

An ideal state is a developmental and progressive-oriented state that constantly invests in its human resources or human capital by developing skills necessary to transform local natural resources into economic goods that meet the needs and expectations of its citizens (Law, 2009; Anderson 2014; Evan & Heller 2018). The ideal state in this context is self-sufficient, self-sustaining and by this gesture (imply an independent status that) can functionally utilise its local skills and retain a significant pool of its human resources for development at home (Cheng 1987; Sim & Ho 2007; Trokanovsky 2019). The ideal development-oriented state is able to channel both capital and other resources, including strong institutional environment and adequate incentives to attract and motivate suitable human resources towards developing their capacity and potential for both the individual and the state to realise sustainable development. Measuring a state's capacity to develop would require the utilisation and combination of indicators or variables of Human Capital Investment index and Human Development Index.

The problem with Nigeria is that it is unable to develop and utilise its abundant human resources or human capital for its own development amidst its abundant natural and mineral resources. Instead, the country is massively underutilising its human resources by creating weak institutional framework that is increasing its emigration of human resources other more advanced states. The migration data identified that a net of 164 people leave Nigeria per day to other states where the incentives to utilise their capacities and earn more rather than remain idle or fallow in Nigeria. For a year the figure will be 59,860 persons leaving the country for better opportunities elsewhere and in ten years, 598,600 persons would leave the country. Consequently, people with much potential and capacity are more likely to leave Nigeria to other countries where their skills are more valued and appreciated as Kunczer, Linner & Puck (2019) identified that skilful immigrants contribute value and advantage to firms' benefits in their destination country. The reason for this line of argument is that advanced countries, especially the United States of American and Canada, where these potentials can be effectively exploited provide adequate incentives for immigrants in the form of scholarship and visa lottery while those without skills and potentials are denied visa, scholarship. Exhibiting

desperation to escape poverty, the latter usually enter their destination country illegally without documentation, significantly leading to deportation on arrival, as it is assumed that without skills to attract opportunities, they are likely to commit crime to survive in a new environment (Gould, Weinberg & Mustard 2002; Hanson, Lui & McIntosh 2017; Connor & Ruiz 2019).

The race and rapidity with which potentials, especially trained care professionals are fleeing Nigeria to other advanced countries have consequences if this trend is unchecked with adequate human resources development policies to retain and utilise same for our development. Nigeria will become a fallow state in anticipation of the potential of an escalating population of 401 million people with more than half of same being poor, unemployed and miserable. This claim was sustained by the Nigerian Medical Association which affirmed that 700 medical doctors leave Nigeria annually. This is for one profession and is replicated every year for diverse fields, including the academia (*The Punch*, 2019). Thus, this study was centred on altering the emergence of a fallow State in Nigeria's Fourth Republic.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine the relationship between the level of human capital investment and sustainable development.
2. Investigate if low human capital investment will induce the emergence of a fallow state.
3. Examine the institutional environment under which a fallow state can emerge.

Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses of the study are stated in null form:

1. There is no relationship between the level of human capital investment and sustainable development.
2. Low human capital investment in Nigeria would not induce the emergence of a fallow state.
3. There is no institutional environment in which a fallow state can emerge.

Conceptual Review and Review of Related Literature

The concept of fallow state is a new lexicon with emerging qualitative description essential to appreciate this paper. A fallow state is an object that is currently not appropriately functional and is put to rest or kept idle because its capacity has been previously abused, overused or misused and has experienced decline or decay in productivity as a factor of production. When an object remains fallow, misused or abused, there is a conscious attempt and deliberate move to shift to another productive object that is considered functional and result-oriented. The decision to make an object fallow is conditioned on the possibility of sourcing for a better means that is comparatively more productive and more relatively functional. A fallow state, in perspective of human resource management, is a state that neglects or mismanages its

human resources to the point where the human capital investment is relatively insignificant to make any meaningful utilisation of its abundant mineral and natural resources to engender development from within or even attract from external sources. It is a state where the active human capital is unable to respond to the challenge of misuse, abuse, underutilisation or non-usage in local productivity and therefore leave the current (territory) state fallow by sourcing for a more conducive environment where its capacity will be put into productive use as well as being appreciated in terms of how much it will be able to earn during the period of being fallow.

It is very incisive to investigate into the role human resources play in the development and sustainability of a modern state. Imahe (2018) captured the relevance of human capital investment by positing that Nigeria should invest in human capital and prosper. Mailafia (2019) similarly expressed that people now constitute the wealth of a nation. Investment in people has tremendous capacity for providing a developmental state that is sustainable. A pull-push factor in attracting or repelling human resources to either make contribution or navigate to where it is attracted is a significant trend in migration studies. Human behaviour is guided by rationalism: it is either attracted to organisation or state by the way or manner it is treated or repelled by the way it is neglected, misused or abused. International migration theory within the spectrum of human capital theory as deployed by Haas (2007) expressed that individuals are relatively aware of their skills, abilities, knowledge, sex as well as opportunities open or available to them in other countries; thus, the requisite labour potential is desperately transited to where it is scarce, needed and valuable. The consequence of increasing population and finding opportunities becomes lesser and highly competitive when other variables like political, economic and social differences produce and reproduce inequality as well as pressure to have a satisfying living.

Acemoglu & Robinson (2012) and Fukuyama (2011, 2014) stressed how weak institutions (political and economic) naturally dissuade investment of human capital because it provides a framework for strengthening the dominating powers of the powerful elites whose vested interest weaken state institutions and prevent inclusiveness in human resources to the making of collective decisions for the state. Fukuyama (2011, 2014) went further to state that powerful political elites by their character capture the state and cause it to decay, while Acemoglu & Robinson (2012) depicted that the state under elites' domination has extractive institutions which prevent the development of individuals' capacity to develop the state through their contribution. Citizens' participation and inclusiveness allow or create the foundation to ask for accountable and transparent government.

Imahe (2018) stated that capital investment consists of investment in health, education and standard of living of people in a particular state. The investment in people enables a state to take advantage of economic opportunities arising from the use of opportunities derived from such investment. It is a long-term investment, measured as human capital indicator (HCI). The World Bank also uses the human capital index (HCI) to measure the level of investment as intervention a state has expended in its human resources. The scale is, therefore, reflective of and also correlates to the Human Development Index (HDI) which measures life expectancy, education and income per capita as basis for accessing a country's development rate. The worst situation or condition for the individual with less investment in education, health and other welfare conditions is to be trapped in poverty. Invariably, we can also measure the human capital

development by assessing the number of people that are poor in a state or the proportion of poverty in a state. We can derive if the state by its policy can induce poverty on its population. Another way to look at the quality of human capital investment is to calculate the misery index which is a multiplication of inflation and unemployment; the misery index captures the number or proportion of miserable people in a state and this is essentially people who, if kept in enabling environment can make meaningful contribution towards the development of a state. Bull (1977) identified that states with high human capital investment have orderly society while states with low capital investment tend to degenerate into anarchical society. In this circumstance, the alternative path is for those with capacity to drift towards orderly society that can appreciate and appropriate their skills with reciprocal benefits.

Theoretical Framework

Complex phenomena as state evolutionary trend are driven by multiple of intervening and interacting variables that require a level of sophistication to properly explain and predict their observable behaviour and predict the pattern that they are likely to take in the future. To properly understand the pattern of Nigeria's trajectory, Ekeh's two republic theory will serve as main theory while Marxism will serve as the auxiliary theory for the theoretical framework to give this research work direction and justification of the issues and pattern that emanate from it. Intuitively and for easy comprehension of the reader; starting with the verse will be in order.

Marxism and the Marxist ideology account for the existence of contradictions in every society or state. It is these contradictions that give rise to opposing classes with variant interests causing an inevitable class struggle that will lead to revolution. Marx & Engel (1973) within the lens of Marxism (being utilised as auxiliary theory in the context of this research) as explored in the communist manifesto, affirmed the existence of two major classes in society. The capitalist bourgeoisie class and the working proletariat class; Marxism identified that the state is an instrument of oppression deployed by the bourgeoisie class to exploit and oppress the proletariat working class. The production and work structure of organisation (social relations of production) render the working class to be constantly exploited to the point where he loses his humanity and he is alienated from the things he produces; consequently, making the proletariat to be helpless and miserable. This condition will continue perpetually until and unless the working class revolutionise and take back the state and the means of production from their masters and captors.

Suffice it to state here that Marx's prediction of withering of the state and the takeover by the working class has not come into fruition, but it has adjusted state or elite behaviour in a piece meal manner. It is heuristic in framing the mode of working organisation and provided a template for how employers now marginally adjust workers' demand to prevailing circumstances. Marx's prediction is premised on the unbearable conditions that workers are cautiously facing as a result of exploitation and alienation in the work place. His offering is total revolution and takeover of the state which serve as the instrument of oppression and the automatic dismantling of the state that in the first place allowed the exploitation to take place unhindered. This prediction has not been possible in Nigeria, considering that Marx hinged his prediction on the unbearable working conditions that workers would cease to tolerate. The sufficient conditions for Marx's call for revolution have been met in Nigeria, but the attempts at revolutions,

including the revolution-now project, have all failed to occur. The answer to this question lies in the major theory applied to this research- Ekeh's theory of two publics.

The Ekeh's theory of two publics provides two variants of one personality in the Nigerian state. Ekeh's theoretical postulation identified that in Nigeria, an individual belongs to two different publics at the same time- the civic public and the primordial public. The civic public represents the ideology and defence of the moral attitude to which one is patriotic to the path of nationalism and nation building. The primordial public represents an alternative ideology and defense of ethnic morals to which the individual finds comfort in the face of competition over limited resources. In a multi-ethnic and plural society like Nigeria, with large population, the struggle and competition over how resources are to be distributed among individuals is a complex process. The integration projection has not been able to unify Nigeria as a single entity. Elites in their character have been able to mobilise the population across the divides of the civic and the primordial publics according to changing circumstances.

According to Ekeh (1975), there is a dialectic tension between the two publics in mobilising the individual as citizen in the civic public and at the same time as indigene of an ethnic group to which he bears sympathy in the primordial publics. The civic public is seen as inexhaustible and requires taking from at all times in order to give/support the primordial publics that is lacking and needing care. The dialectic confrontation of the civic and primordial public has weakened public institutions against the primordial ethnic institutions that mobilise resources from the former to the latter. It is this weakening of the civic public institutions that have created inefficient and exploitative trends where a rich state produces poor working conditions for those outside its primordial public. Revolution is inherently not possible within the context of the dialectics of the two publics and effective mobilisation and allocation of civic resources based on merit and rationalism is painfully not feasible in Nigeria, unless the residue of the monster of primordial public is restricted or exorcised. The failure of cohesive and coherent unified Nigerian state has fostered distortions and undermined the possibility to properly invest on citizenship identifying with the state, but rather exploiting the civic public for the primordial public. State resources are, therefore, not concentrated in creating a robust economy that is inclusive and directed on the long-run in investing in human resources for sustainable development. Much of the state policies are redistributive to ethnic orregional groups with primordial interests. This condition tends to generate more of inequality as it reproduces not essential a class struggle as Marx has predicted, but a preponderance of multifarious wastage on primordial projects and programmes with no investment priority and development for the future.

Methodology

The researcher relied on survey from secondary data extracted from Human Capital Index and Human Development Index of 189 countries (reflecting the population of study) divided into two groups. Ten countries (sample size), comprising Five Rich Developed Countries and Five Poor Developing countries were drawn from the 2017/2018 HDI report to study the emerging pattern of how HCI and HDI are related and how the direction or magnitude of their relationship and movement can measure and account for a country's level of development. A graphic correlation analysis of the HCI and HDI was presented to show how the two variables (level -high or low- of investment help explain the pattern of human development that a country is trapped in.

Data Collection and Analysis

Country/Territory		HDI	HCI ^[1] 2018
2017 data rankings ^[1]	2018 report	2017 data rankings ^[1]	2018 report
1	Norway	0.953	▲ 0.77
2	Switzerland	0.944	▲ 0.77
12	Canada	0.926	▲ 0.80

Country/Territory		HDI	HCI ^[1] 2018
2017 data rankings ^[1]	2018 report	2017 data rankings ^[1]	2018 report
13	United States	0.924	▲ 0.76
14	United Kingdom	0.922	▲ 0.78
154	Tanzania	0.538	▼ 0.40
156	Zimbabwe	0.535	▼ 0.44
157	Nigeria	0.532	▼ 0.34
187	South Sudan	0.388	▼ 0.30
189	Niger	0.354	▼ 0.32

Sources: Human Development Report 2018 – Human Development Indices and Indicators

The Human Capital Index (HCI),

<https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/dataset/human-capital-index>

Fig 1: HDI AND HCI correlation graph

Source: Author’s Compilation 2019

Of the 189 countries surveyed, a summary of 10 countries with 5 high human capital investment figures and 5 low human capital investment figures, the table indicated that there is a significant and positive relationship between the level of human capital

investment as reflected in HCI column and the HDI column, the level of investment in Norway 0.77, Switzerland 0.77, Canada 0.80, United States 0.76 and United Kingdom 0.78 tend to produce 0.953, 0.944, 0.926, 0.924 and 0.922 level of development respectively. This indicated that the high level of investment correlates and corresponds with high level of development above average. Likewise, maintaining the above trend, the table also indicated that Tanzania with 0.40, Zimbabwe 0.44, Nigeria 0.34, South Sudan 0.30 and Niger with 0.32 produced 0.538, 0.535, 0.532, 0.388 and 0.354 level of investment respectively. The result also indicated that low level of investment will account for low level of development. The above result rejected hypothesis one that stated that there is no relationship between the level of human capital investment and sustainable development and thus, accepted that there is a positive and significant relationship between the level of investment and sustainable development since the education, health and standard of living of the participant countries signify a pattern that indicates that variation in the volume of spending is relatively proportional to the level of investment. This result is in tandem with Imahie (2018) and Mailafia (2019) which expressed that human capital investment accounts for a country's ability to prosper and also sustain its development.

Testing hypothesis two which states that "low human capital investment in Nigeria would not induce the emergence of a fallow state" is rejected. Nigeria's human capital investment index in fig 1.1 is 0.34 which is low investment and when correlated with human development index, Nigeria's score is 0.532 with a ranking of 157 out of 189. The low level of investment in Nigeria has strong correlation with low level of skills, capacity and resources to drive development and sustain it. Nigeria's major economy stay, oil and gas sector is dominated by foreigners because there is lack of skills or resourcefulness in that sector. Nigeria's economy is also highly dependent on external products for lack of capacity to produce those products at home. Poverty, unemployment and inequality are high in Nigeria and you cannot call this circumstance development (Todaro & Smit, 2011). Following the instability caused by the dialectical confrontation between primordial public and the civil public in Nigeria, the production of weak and extractive institutions continue to discourage the investment of human capital in Nigeria and the drifting away of capable skills for better and secure means of livelihood since the chances of being trapped in the poverty equation is high. Institutions in Nigeria are driven more by primordial sentiments than civil values, so the question of allowing capable human resources to drive development is out of the equation. Migrating to an alternative country that will appreciate and encourage further investment and attract better earnings is inevitable. The rapidity with which Nigerians are fleeing the country abroad signifies that within a stretch of another 30 years there is the possibility that the Nigerian state will be fallow. The result is in concord with Fukuyama (2011, p. 14) that classified Nigeria as a decayed state with uncontrollable institution that is unable to provide a hegemonic agenda that is progressive towards inclusive development. People will naturally drift away from a decayed state and the consequence is that a fallow state will emerge in its place.

Testing of hypothesis three is based on the stated claim that "there is no institutional environment in which a fallow state can emerge in Nigeria." Following the discussed literature, extractive institutions readily provide the environment through which a fallow state can emerge in Nigeria as comparative data have shown in the discussed table that Nigeria ranked 157 out of 189 countries surveyed for Human Development

Index and relatively measured 0.34 value which represents about 34% of what is spent on development effort. An abysmal gap of 66% is lacking for human capital development. Acemoglu & Robinson (2012) identified that weak institutions that are extractive rather than inclusive tend to be underdeveloped and people are alienated from exploring their potentials.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study focused on altering the emergence of a fallow state in Nigeria's Fourth Republic with reference to human resources management. The conclusion reached based on the analysis of the table and the correlation of human capital investment and human development index is that there is a significant and positive relationship between human capital investment and sustainable development. The study also established that low investment in human capital can induce the emergence of a fallow since the primordial public offset the quest of the civil public in Nigeria by allowing a continuous migration of skilled labour to other advanced countries. The researcher recommends that a fifty-year human capital investment and development strategy be put in place to induce sustainable development to take place. There is need to jettison the Federal Character Principle that is obsolete because it tends to promote mediocrity, allowing for a quota and rotational system that creates a recruitment policy in public service that sacrifices the best for the weak and dispel meritocracy which accounts for why capable potentials that would stay and contribute to Nigeria's development drive and sustainability are leaving in droves to more advanced countries.

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